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PRIMARY CRACKS IN ATOMICALLY SMOOTH CRYSTALS OF ALKALINE ELEMENTS

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ПЕРВИЧНЫЕ ТРЕЩИНЫ В АТОМАРНО-ГЛАДКИХ КРИСТАЛЛОВ ЩЕЛОЧНЫХ ЭЛЕМЕНТОВ

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Abstract

An alkali metal crystal consists of a surface layer of size $R(I)$, which we will call the σ_1 phase, and a base material, which we will call the σ_2 phase. Since the surface energy of the layer $R(I)$ with σ_1 is 2 times less than the surface energy of the bulk phase, the destruction of the metal starts from the surface layer. Moreover, for an alkali metal, destruction begins from the (111) face. For crystals with identical atoms, the share of space occupied by them in one cube is 68% for alkali metals. The rest (32%) is occupied by empty space. After relaxation, we will call this space the maximum field of primary cracks. For us, the most important thing is the fact that the length of this crack L is equal to the thickness of the surface layer of the alkali metal $R(I)$. This crack length reflects the peculiarity that it is associated not only with the geometry of crystal lattices, but also with the physical properties of crystals. We have proposed a model for calculating the length of primary cracks that appear in metals due to the presence of a surface layer $R(I)$. Griffiths considered the change in the energy of a body with a crack under loading and obtained an energy criterion for failure. Our calculation of the crack length L for lithium Li gave $L = 2.6$ nm. For lithium Li, the average crack length is $L = 2.2$ nm, which does not differ much from our formula. This is to talk about the validity of our model.

Аннотация

Кристалл щелочного металла состоит из поверхностного слоя размером $R(I)$, который мы назовем фазой σ_1 , и основного вещества, который мы назовем фазой σ_2 . Поскольку поверхностная энергия слоя $R(I)$

с σ_1 в 2 раза меньше поверхностной энергии объемной фазы, то разрушение металла начинается с поверхностного слоя. Причем для щелочного металла разрушение начинается с грани (111). Для кристаллов с одинаковыми атомами доля пространства, занятого ими в одном кубе составляет для щелочных металлов - 68 %. Остальная часть (32 %) занято пустым пространством. После релаксации это пространство мы и будем называть максимальным полем первичных трещин. Для нас, самое главное, это тот факт, что длина этой трещины L равна толщине поверхностного слоя щелочного металла $R(I)$. Эта длина трещины отражает ту особенность, что она связана не только с геометрией кристаллических решеток, но и физическими свойствами кристаллов. Нами предложена модель расчета длины первичных трещин, возникающих в металлах из-за наличия поверхностного слоя $R(I)$. Гриффитс рассмотрел изменение энергии тела с трещиной при нагружении и получил энергетический критерий разрушения. Наш расчет длины трещины L для лития Li дал $L = 2,6$ нм. Для лития Li среднее значение длины трещины $L = 2,2$ нм, что не сильно отличается от нашей формулы. Это говорит о справедливости нашей модели.

Keywords: Surface layer, crack, alkali metal, energy, model, surface, crystal, fracture.

Ключевые слова: Поверхностный слой, трещина, щелочной металл, энергия, модель, поверхность, кристалл, разрушение.

Introduction

Alkali metals are elements of group 1 of the periodic table of chemical elements. Of these, lithium in compounds is used in current sources and batteries; sodium in compounds is used in the chemical and food industries, the production of organic acids; potassium

in compounds is used as a fertilizer and in medicine; rubidium and cesium are used in optics, and cesium is used in atomic clocks. The main properties of alkali metals that we will use in the article are shown in Table 1. All alkali metals are stored either under vacuum or in an inert atmosphere in sealed ampoules (Fig. 1).

Table 1.

Physical properties of alkali metals

Element/property	Li	Na	K	Rb	Cs
M (g/mol) - molar mass	6,997	22,989	39,098	85,467	132,905
ρ (g/cm ³) - density	0,534	0,971	0,856	1,532	1,873
Structure	Im3m	Im3m	Im3m	Im3m	Im3m
Lattice parameters (nm)	0,349	0,428	0,533	0,571	0,614
T _m (K) - melting point	453,69	370,96	336,80	312,45	301,7
E (GPa) - Young modulus	4,9	4,0	3,53	2,4	1,7

Figure 1. Alkali metal crystals.

The electron shells of alkaline atoms have a single electron. Due to the very small ionization potential, atoms easily give it away, and are present in nature in the form of ions, the only valence in this group is +1. Their mechanical properties are presented in table 2. Thus, an

isotropic material is characterized by four elastic constants μ , E , G , K , of which only two are independent. Poisson's ratio $0 < \mu < 0.5$; E - Young's modulus, $G = E/2(1+\mu)$ - shear modulus, $K = E/3(1-2\mu)$ - bulk modulus.

Mechanical properties of alkali metals

Element/property	Li	Na	K	Rb	Cs
G (GPa) - shear modulus	4,2	3,3	1,3	-	-
K - volumetric module elasticity (GPa)	11	6,3	3,1	2,5	1,6
Mohs hardness	0,6	0,5	0,4	0,3	0,2
Brinell hardness (MPa)	5	0,69	0,363	0,216	0,140

In this article, the concept of atomically smooth crystals is presented and the length of primary and spatial cracks in alkali metals is presented for the first time.

Atomically smooth surfaces of alkali metals.

When splitting single crystals in vacuum along the cleavage plane, three types of surfaces can form: singular (atomically smooth), vicinal (stepped), nonsingular (diffuse) surfaces (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Three types of surfaces: singular (atomically smooth)-1, vicinal (stepped)-2, non-singular (diffuse) surfaces-3 [12].

On singular surfaces, the transition from the solid phase to the vapor phase occurs within one layer, on vicinal surfaces, the transition occurs through several crystallographic planes separated by monoatomic steps, and on diffusion surfaces, the transition from the solid to the vapor phase occurs over several atomic layers. However, the layer thickness is unknown. The study of such surfaces became possible after the development of ultrahigh vacuum technology, atomic force and tunneling spectroscopy [3]. On the surface of alkali metals, surface atoms turn out to be uncompensated with atoms that are in the volume (Fig. 3a) [1, 2]. Therefore, there is a relaxation of the surface layers, which is considered

in detail in [4]. Moreover, the relaxed surface is characterized only by a change in the interplanar distances d_{ij} (Fig. 3b). It is emphasized in [4]: despite the shortcomings of the methods for calculating surface relaxation, they made it possible to obtain important qualitative results. First, it became possible to give a definite answer to the question of which forces and in what direction act on the ions of the surface plane: in the absence of relaxation, the electrostatic Madelung forces try to move the surface into the crystal, while the electronic forces try to push it into vacuum. If the distance d_{12} is sufficiently reduced, then these forces act in the opposite direction.

Figure 3. Atoms on the surface and in the volume (a); schematic illustration of normal (left) and lateral (right) relaxations of the upper atomic layer of a semi-infinite crystal [1, 2].

The real value of d_{12} is obtained when these forces are equal. Secondly, an important conclusion was drawn about the strong effect of screening by electron density on the equilibrium position of ions, about the need to take into account the adiabaticity of the relaxation process, and about serious shortcomings of calculations with a “frozen” charge density profile. Thirdly, the general tendency of relaxation anisotropy has been established: more closely packed surfaces relax less. Fourth, it is shown that several layers of the lattice can participate in relaxation. Multilayer relaxation has an

oscillating character (the first interplanar distance d_{12} is, as a rule, reduced, the second d_{23} is increased relative to the bulk one), the oscillation period is equal to the packing period of the layers parallel to the surface. Table 3 for Na relaxation is given in [4]. On fig. 4 shows the amplitude of charge density oscillations and the wave function of this state is increased near the surface (Figure 4 a, b). Surface states do not fall into the narrow slit of the projection K. The level closest to the gap with the accuracy of calculation (0.01 Ry) coincides with its bottom, its charge density has a resonant form (Fig. 4c).

a - Na; surface point (001). b - Li; surface point (001). surface resonance, surface point (001). d - Li; surface point (111). Dark circles are atoms in planes parallel to the surface.

Figure 4. Charge density of surface states [4].

Table 3.

Values of relaxation of metal surfaces M (i, j are the numbers of atomic layers, counting from the surface) as a percentage with respect to the volumetric interplanar distance.

Minus sign - decrease, plus - increase d_{ij} [4].

M	(hkl)	d_{ij}	M	(hkl)	d_{ij}	M	(hkl)	d_{ij}
Na	(001)	$d_{12}=-2,7$	Na	(011)	$d_{12}=-0,3$	Na	(111)	$d_{12}=-8$
		$d_{23}=0,7$			$d_{23}=0,1$			$d_{23}=-29$
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	$d_{24}=23$

It follows from Figure 3 that an alkali metal crystal consists of a surface layer R(I), which we will call the σ_1 phase, and the main substance, which we will call the σ_2 phase (Fig. 5a).

Figure 3. Alkali metal crystal phases (a) and work of adhesion (b).

The surface energy of the bulk phase σ_2 can be calculated with high accuracy using the formula given in the works (Fig. 4a) [5, 6]:

$$\sigma_2 = 0.7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m (K), \quad (J/m^2) \quad (1)$$

where $T_m (K)$ is the melting point (Table 1).

To calculate σ_1 using formula (1), it is necessary to take into account the size dependence of the melting temperature (Fig. 4b) using the formulas [6]:

$$T_m (h) = T_m (K) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R(I)}{h} \right), \quad h \gg R(I) \quad (2)$$

$$T_m (h) = T_m (K) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R(I)}{R(I) + h} \right), \quad 0 \leq h \leq R(I).$$

$$\text{Im}3m, Z = 2, l_{100} = R(I), l_{110} = R(I)\sqrt{2}, l_{111} = R(I)/\sqrt{3} \quad (4)$$

Using equations (1) - (4) and table 1, we present the parameters of alkali metals in table 4. For the specific energy of destruction of the metal, one must take the amount of absorbed energy at which this metal has a complete exhaustion of resistance to external forces,

where $T_m (K)$ is the melting temperature of the bulk sample, h is the layer coordinate.

The adhesion energy is given by Dupre's expression [7]:

$$W_a = \sigma_1 + \sigma_2 - \sigma_{12} \approx \sigma_1 + \sigma_2, \quad (J/m^2) \quad (3)$$

where σ_{12} is the surface energy at the phase boundary, which is negligible due to the second order phase transition.

Moreover, for a cubic body-centered lattice of alkali metals, the equality takes place [8]:

i.e. full loss of the metal of its bearing capacity. According to E. Orovan [10], the intensity of material destruction is determined by the adhesion energy:

$$W(hkl) = 2\sigma(hkl) \quad [J/m^2] \quad (5)$$

Figure 4. Correlative dependence of surface tension (surface energy σ) on melting temperature [5]; size dependence of Au temperature (b) [9].

Table 4.

Adhesion energy W_a of alkali metals.

Metal	(hkl)	$\sigma_1, J/m^2$	$\sigma_2, J/m^2$	$W_a, J/m^2$
Li	(100)	0.159	0.318	0.477
	(110)	0.186	0.445	0.631
	(111)	0.118	0.187	0.305
Na	(100)	0.137	0.260	0.397
	(110)	0.160	0.364	0.534
	(111)	0.100	0.153	0.253
K	(100)	0.118	0.236	0.354
	(110)	0.138	0.330	0.468
	(111)	0.087	0.139	0.226
Rb	(100)	0.109	0.218	0.327
	(110)	0.127	0.305	0.432
	(111)	0.081	0.128	0.209
Cs	(100)	0.106	0.211	0.317
	(110)	0.123	0.295	0.418
	(111)	0.078	0.124	0.202

Since the energy of the layer R(I) is 2 times less than the surface energy of the bulk phase, the destruction of the metal begins from the surface. Moreover, for an alkali metal, destruction begins from the (111) face. The adhesion energy is of interest in calculating the internal stresses of alkali metals, which arise due to the presence of a surface of size R(I). Internal stresses ϵ_{is} between phases σ_1 and σ_2 can be calculated using the formula [7]:

$$\epsilon_{is} = \sqrt{[W_a / R(I)] \cdot E} \quad (\text{Pa}) \quad (6)$$

And the size R(I) is determined by the formula [6]:

$$R(I) = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \nu \quad (\text{m}) \quad (7)$$

where $\nu = M/\rho$, M is the molar mass, ρ is the density of the metal.

In formula (6), all values are given in table 1. Then the average value of the internal stresses for alkali metals is presented in table 5. The adhesion force for alkali metals is:

$$F_1 = \sigma_1 \cdot R(I). \quad (8)$$

From Table 5 that the R(I) layer is a nanostructure. The thickness of the surface layer R(I) for a cubic body-centered lattice of alkali metals is maximum in the (110) plane and minimum in the (111) plane. It increases in the series Li \rightarrow Cs according to equation (7) with an increase in the molar volume (Fig. 4a). In Table 5, at R(I), the values $n = R(I)/a$ (a is the lattice constant) of alkali metal monolayers are given in parentheses.

Table 5.

Surface layer thickness $R(I)$, adhesion force F_1 , values of internal stresses ϵ_{is} .

Metal	(hkl)	$R(I)$, nm	F_1 , nN	ϵ_{is} , MPa
Li	(100)	2.2 (6)	0.35	1062
	(110)	3.1 (9)	0.58	997
	(111)	1.3 (4)	0.15	1072
Na	(100)	4.5 (11)	0.62	939
	(110)	6.3 (15)	1.01	921
	(111)	2.6 (6)	0.26	968
K	(100)	7.7 (15)	0.91	402
	(110)	10.8 (21)	1.49	391
	(111)	4.5 (9)	0.39	421
Rb	(100)	10.0 (18)	1.09	279
	(110)	14.0 (25)	1.78	272
	(111)	5.9 (10)	0.48	292
Cs	(100)	12.1 (20)	1.28	212
	(110)	16.9 (24)	2.08	205
	(111)	7.1 (12)	0.55	219

Figure 4. Periodic change in the atomic volume of elements (a); sound audibility area (b).

The adhesion force (the force of intermolecular interaction) is maximum for cesium in the (110) plane - $F_1 = 2.08 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N. For comparison: the force of attraction between an electron and a proton in a hydrogen atom is $F = 0.2 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N; sound pressure strength in the human ear at the threshold of hearing - $F = 2 \cdot 10^{-9}$ N (Fig. 4b); locomotive traction force $F = 6 \cdot 10^5$ N; force of attraction between the Earth and the Moon $F = 2 \cdot 10^{20}$ N.

According to I.V. Kragelsky [11], the friction force of metals F_{tr} consists of two components: the intermolecular interaction force F_1 (formula 8) and the mechanical force F_2 , which represents a load normal to the friction plane:

$$F_{tr} = f \cdot (F_1 + F_2), \quad (9)$$

where f is the coefficient of friction.

The value of internal stresses ϵ_{is} (Table 5) decreases significantly in the series $Li \rightarrow Cs$. This indicates that an increase in density (Table 1) leads to an increase in relaxation in the surface layer and an increase in interlayer interactions, which is confirmed by the study of the phonon spectrum carried out in [12]. The value of internal

stresses ϵ_{is} (Table 5) is an order of magnitude smaller than the bulk modulus of elasticity K and shear modulus G (Table 2), as well as Young's modulus (Table 1).

For crystals with identical atoms, the share of space occupied by them in one cube is 68% for alkali metals. The rest (32%) is occupied by empty space. After relaxation, we will call this space the maximum field of primary cracks. For us, the most important thing is the fact that the length of this crack L is equal to the thickness of the surface layer of the alkali metal $R(I)$. This crack length reflects the peculiarity that it is associated not only with the geometry of crystal lattices, but also with the physical properties of crystals, namely: with the type of chemical bond (ionic, covalent, metallic, etc.); porosity, anisotropy and other properties.

After lateral relaxation (Fig. 3), a perpendicular crack appears (Fig. 5a), and during normal relaxation (Fig. 3), a parallel crack appears (Fig. 5b). Their simultaneous action leads to a network structure of cracks (Fig. 5c).

Figure 5. Perpendicular (a), parallel (b), mesh cracks (c).

Model of primary cracks in alkali metal crystals.

It was shown above that the crack length L is equal to the thickness of the alkali metal surface layer $R(I)$, the value of which was determined in [6]:

$$L = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \nu. \text{ (m)} \quad (10)$$

Theoretically, in a layer consisting of one-dimensional spherical particles, the average pore size will be equal to the size of the empty space formed with a single-layer staggered arrangement of three spheres. The pore radius, in this case, is equal to:

$$r = 0,154 \cdot L. \text{ (m)} \quad (11)$$

When the particles are in the form of spheres of the same diameter L , the specific surface area S_{sp} is given by:

$$S_{sp} = 6 / \rho \cdot L. \text{ (m}^2/\text{g)} \quad (12)$$

Parameters (10) - (12) are presented in Table 6.

The microcrack length L increases in the series $Li \rightarrow Cs$ and is a nanostructure. These microcracks can be compared with edge and screw dislocations that arise during lateral and normal relaxation of the surface (see above) (Fig. 6). The dislocations (microcracks) noted

above are localized in the R(I) nanostructured layer, which is characterized by quantum regularities [13]. According to this work, there is an opinion that the formation of microcracks in the R(I) layer can be not only dislocations, but also displacement waves (see Fig. 4). These damped waves arise due to vibrations of atoms in the process of relaxation and are shown by us in Fig. 7a. As a result of photoexcitation with photon energy $h\nu$, the spectrum of photoelectrons excited and released into vacuum in the direction of quantization of the electronic structure of the film (i.e., in the z direction) will repeat the energy distribution of the density of electronic states determined by the condition for the formation of the corresponding standing electron waves (Fig. 7c and the formula (13)).

$$E_n = \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m^*} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m^*} \left(\frac{\pi n}{L} \right)^2 \quad (13)$$

where $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ is the quantum number characterizing the multiplicity of the wavelength of the emerging standing waves (different modes) with respect to the dimensions L of the potential box, m^* is the electron mass.

Table 6.

Crack length, pore size, specific surface area of SM				
Metal	(hkl)	L, nm	r, nm	S_{sp} , m ² /g
Li	(100)	2.2	0.34	5,11
	(110)	3.1	0.48	3.62
	(111)	1.3	0.20	8.64
Na	(100)	4.5	0.69	1.37
	(110)	6.3	0.97	0.98
	(111)	2.6	0.40	2.38
K	(100)	7.7	1.19	0.91
	(110)	10.8	1.66	0.65
	(111)	4.5	0.69	1.56
Rb	(100)	10.0	1.54	0.39
	(110)	14.0	2.16	0.28
	(111)	5.9	0.91	0.66
Cs	(100)	12.1	1.86	0.26
	(110)	16.9	2.60	0.19
	(111)	7.1	1.09	0.45

Figure 6. Screw dislocation model (a), edge dislocation AB in a crystal (b). The arrow shows the direction of the shear stress [1].

Figure 7. Damped waves in the R(I) layer (a); the processes of quantization of the electronic structure from the standpoint of the formation of a discrete set of standing waves in the layer R(I) (c) [14].

It should also be noted that the spectrum of quantum states is discrete only in the direction of limiting the wave functions in the film (z) (Fig. 7c, a). In directions along the film (x, y), where there are no dimensional restrictions, the electronic spectrum is a set of parabolas with the dispersion law $E = \hbar^2 k^2 / 2m^*$ with energy minima corresponding to the energies of quantum states in the z direction (Fig. 7c, b) [14]. It follows from Fig. 3 that all physical properties of the nanostructured layer $\sigma_1 = R(I)$ have size effects like Fig. 4b. We are interested in the size effects of mechanical quantities (Fig. 8a). In polycrystalline metals, the influence of the average grain size d on the yield strength σ is usually described using the Hall-Petch relation [15, 16]:

$$\sigma_0 = \sigma_i + \hat{E} \cdot d^{-1/2}, \quad (14)$$

where σ_0 is the stress that characterizes the resistance to plastic deformation on the part of the crystal lattice and lattice defects that prevent the movement of lattice dislocations; K is the coefficient characterizing the contribution to hardening from the grain boundaries.

In [17], for the yield strength of nanocrystals, we obtained:

$$\sigma_0 = \sigma_i + C \cdot \sigma \cdot d^{-1/2}. \quad (15)$$

Equation (15) coincides in form with the Hall-Petch equation (14). However, the coefficients of proportionality in both formulas are different. In the case under consideration, the behavior of the yield strength of small particles is also determined by their surface energy σ according to formula (1). For the R(I) layer, A.I. Rusanov obtained a linear dependence [18]:

$$\sigma = K \cdot d. \quad (16)$$

Here K is the coefficient of proportionality. Formula (16) was obtained on the basis of thermodynamic consideration and should be applicable to small objects of various nature. In this case, (15) takes the form:

$$\sigma_0 = \sigma_i + C \cdot K \cdot d^{1/2}. \quad (17)$$

Equation (17) is the inverse Hall-Petch effect (Fig. 8b). Thus, the reverse Hall-Petch effect is due to the size dependence of the surface energy of nanoparticles and nanostructures, which is determined by the Rusanov formula (16).

Figure 8. Spatial limitation of wave functions in two-dimensional (2D), one-dimensional (1D) and zero-dimensional (0D) systems (a); inverse Hall-Petch effect on the copper nanostructure (b) [17].

The pore size r (Table 6) increases in the series Li \rightarrow Cs in accordance with formula (11), where $r \sim L$. According to the IUPAC definition, porous bodies are divided into microporous (pore diameter less than 2 nm), mesoporous (ranging from 2 to 50 nm) and macroporous (more than 50 nm) [19]. In our case (Table 6) we have microporous alkali metals. The exceptions are Rb (2.16 nm) and Cs (2.60 nm) along the (110) plane, where the alkali metals are mesoporous structures. In materials subjected to deformation, it is customary to distinguish the following mechanisms of pore formation [20]:

- due to the merging of dislocation cracks, which are formed during the deceleration of slip planes;
- due to the formation of steps on the grain boundaries at the exit point of the sliding planes with subsequent sliding along the boundary;

- due to coagulation of vacancies;
- due to the annihilation of dislocations in opposite planes of the cluster, spaced from each other by 5-7 Burgers vectors.

A common mechanism for the formation of pores is through the formation of local accumulations of vacancies with their subsequent condensation into pores. Therefore, the pore can be considered as a complex of vacancies.

As mentioned above, the crack length (Table 6) is formed due to the formation of dislocations. The mechanism of dislocation formation is one of the least studied issues in the theory of crystal lattice imperfections [20]. The interaction of dislocations with each other and with crystal defects is of particular interest (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Types of microdiscontinuities: (a) - elastic crack, (b) - dislocation crack, (c) - pore [21].

Griffiths [21] considered the change in the energy of a body with a crack under loading and obtained an energy fracture criterion, according to which a crack acquires the ability to spontaneously propagate only when the rate of release of elastic energy during growth becomes equal to or exceeds the energy of the newly formed surface:

$$\Delta W = \frac{\sigma_{cr}^2 \pi L^2}{2E} + 2\sigma L \quad (18)$$

- total energy change for the case of a plane stress state, where σ - specific surface energy, E - Young's modulus, σ_{cr} - applied stress, L - crack size, ν - Poisson's ratio.

The value of critical stresses at which a crack is capable of unstable growth can be found from the conditions:

$$\frac{\partial W}{\partial L} = 0, \quad \frac{\sigma_{cr}^2 \pi L}{E} = 2\sigma. \quad (19)$$

Let us calculate the crack length L for lithium Li from formula (19) using the data in Table 1. 1, 4, 5, with $\sigma = \sigma_1 + \sigma_2$ and $\sigma_{cr} = \varepsilon_{is}$. As a result, we have $L = 2.6$ nm. For lithium Li, the crack length L is 2.2 nm (100), 3.1 nm (110), and 1.3 nm (111). The average value $L = 2.2$ nm, which does not differ much from formula (19). This is to talk about the validity of our model.

According to [21], the Griffith criterion does not explain the reasons for the existence of stable cracks with finite sizes in crystalline materials, but only indicates the stress level above which the crack is capable of growing, i.e. it is a condition for the loss of stability of a sample with a crack.

Let us briefly present the main provisions of the model proposed by Straw [22]. When using the force criterion, Straw believed that local stresses should be

sufficient to overcome the repulsion between the two head dislocations of the cluster (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. Scheme of microcrack initiation in the Straw model: (a) - initial dislocation cluster, (b) - merging of two head dislocations, (c) - crack growth due to the dumping of most of the cluster dislocations into it [23].

Advantages of the Straw model: the possibility of microcrack initiation due to the merging of dislocations is theoretically substantiated. It is shown that, under the action of applied stresses, most of the dislocations are capable of falling into an incipient crack. This leads to the initiation of a microcrack with a size of $\approx 1 \mu\text{m}$ [24]. However, the quantitative results of the theory showed a significant discrepancy with experiments. This is primarily due to the fact that the length of the microcrack at Stroh is overestimated by two or three orders of magnitude (see Table 6).

Cottrell [25] proposed a scheme for the transformation of dislocations located in intersecting slip systems into a flat pileup of cleavage dislocations capable

of opening into a wedge-shaped crack upon further deformation (Fig. 11a). This scheme is based on the assumption that a crack appears at the intersection of two slip planes by merging the first pair of dislocations sliding in them according to the reaction $a/2[111] + a/2[1\bar{1}1] \Rightarrow a[001]$ with subsequent attachment to dislocation $a[001]$ of other gliding dislocations. Because such a reaction lowers the total energy of the interacting dislocations and thus satisfies the Frank dislocation stability criterion, it is carried out without difficulty.

Figure 11. Scheme of crack formation at the intersection of two dislocations [25] (a); an example of a deformation map of nickel [26] (b): A – dislocation slip without the participation of return; B - dislocation creep (diffusion along the cores of dislocations); C – dislocation creep (bulk diffusion); D – Nabarro-Herring diffusion creep; E is Koble's diffusion creep.

In [25], the role of thermal fluctuations in the initiation of microcracks according to the Cottrell scheme was emphasized, but no formulas like (19) were obtained in the framework of such a model. In [20, 21, 26] and a number of other works, various models of microcrack formation are noted: the Zener-Straw-Petch model, the Cottrell model, the Ballaf-Gilman model, the Orvan-Straw model, the Koble model, and the Nabarro-Herring model. In conclusion, we note that the healing of pores and cracks in crystalline materials under conditions of static or dynamic compression at medium temperatures occurs according to the dislocation mechanism (Fig. 11b).

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Conclusion.

Most of the works on the formation of microcracks in solids, starting from the work of Griffiths (20s of the last century), did not give a quantitative estimate of the length of this microcrack. We have shown that the primary microcrack arises due to the lack of compensation with the atoms that are in the volume. In this case, a surface layer $R(I)$ arises, in which atomic relaxation occurs and internal stresses arise, leading to the appearance of dislocations. These dislocations lead to the formation of pores and microcracks, the length of which depends on the mass and density of the chemical element of the crystal.

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